

Health risks by (micro)plastics in food: Towards a sustainable attitude change in consumer behavior

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Abstract. The present work highlights an approach towards sustainable consumption awareness and attitude change in consumer behavior related to the selection, use, disposal and/or recycling of food packaging. An intervention is designed aiming to lead high school students in adopting a sustainable consumer behavior/lifestyle and increase their science capital. Students cooperate with their families and with scientists in the field. Specific goals and targets of the United Nations' 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development are taken into account. The implementation of the Care-Know-Do framework for open schooling, supporting the intervention, is demonstrated. An attitude change evaluation process is also proposed.

1. Introduction

A significant fraction of the global plastic production is related to food packaging [1-3]. Chemicals found in plastic packaging span a wide and diverse set of materials and origins. Besides the various polymers used, there are also substances deliberately added by the manufacturers, i.e., plasticizers, dyes, lubricants and others, in order to produce plastics with desired properties. Furthermore, non intentionally added chemicals can accumulate as byproducts in food packaging, such as manufacturing residues, monomers, oligomers and other impurities.

Health risks do not only originate from food contamination due to its contact with plastic packaging. Materials used in everyday activities such as clothes, paints, bags, bottles, straws, microbeads for cosmetic, personal care and cleaning products, even tire dust can release microplastics to the environment. Microplastics are microparticles less than 5 millimeters in size [1] that invade in the food chain usually being undetected.

Besides the widespread use of plastics in food packaging and the possible threats to human health, motivating factors for this work have also been: i) The need to raise awareness and comply with the global goals for sustainable development, ii) The availability of bioplastics and biodegradable plastics that could replace the conventional plastics used in food packaging [4], iii) The necessity to update the current recycling patterns in order to include recyclable bioplastics, iv) The significance of packaging labels awareness towards responsible use, deposit/recycling, v) The availability of the infrastructure

and the expertise of the University of Crete which can enhance the science capital of students as well as their interest and confidence in science and vi) The challenge to change human behavior.

According to United Nations' 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are an urgent call for action by all countries in a global partnership for peace and prosperity [5]. Among the SDGs of the 2030 Agenda, the design of the intervention to high- school students and their families presented in this work focuses especially to goal 3: *Good health and well being*, goal 4: *Quality education*, goal 9: *Industry, innovation and infrastructure* and goal 12: *Responsible consumption and production*. The targets under consideration associated with these goals are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Targets of sustainable development goals (SDGs) that shaped the structure of the intervention presented in this work

Goal	Target
3	3.9 Reduce illnesses and death from hazardous chemicals and pollution
4	4.7 Education for sustainable development and global citizenship
9	9.4 Upgrade all industries and infrastructures for sustainability 9.5 Enhance research and upgrade industrial technologies
12	12.4 Responsible management of chemicals and waste 12.5 Substantially reduce waste generation 12.6 Encourage companies to adopt sustainable practices and sustainability reporting 12.8 Promote universal understanding of sustainable lifestyles

The first approach of actions regarding the sustainable use of plastic, in compliance with the abovementioned SDGs, is the approach of 3R's: REDUCE, REUSE, RECYCLE. A second approach is the use of biodegradable polymers. The use of (bio)degradable plastics and bioplastics could, under certain conditions, provide solution to the food contamination and microplastics pollution problem and comply with the SDGs and the associated targets. Biodegradable polymers can be completely degraded by bacterial decomposition being converted into water, CO₂, N₂, inorganic salts as well as biomass. In this sense, after decomposition they return back to nature as a set of natural byproducts. Bioplastics can be one or a combination of the following [4]: i) monomers derived from renewable resources (biomass) and subsequently polymerized chemically, ii) polymers extracted from biomass, iii) biodegradable polymers/plastics and iv) plastic material produced through biological procedures. In general, the raw materials for bioplastics can be:

- Starch and sugars (corn, potatoes, rice, sugarcane)
- Fat and oils (oilseed rape, castor oil, soya oil)
- Cellulose (wood, cotton)
- Proteins (chitin, wheat gluten, silk)
- Biomass

The oceans' algae also appear as a promising raw material candidate containing polysaccharides and reproducing very fast all the year without interference in the food chain. Although not all bioplastics are biodegradable, they are derived from renewable resources. Conventional plastics, on the other hand, are usually derived by fossil fuels. They are often non degradable. Based on non renewable resources, more than nine million barrels of fossil fuel are needed daily for the plastic we are using. This excessive use of fossil fuels also contributes to the global warming.

Environmental issues appear in the use of bioplastics as well. The bioplastics production strongly depends upon oil fuel, which is needed as energy source for the operation of agricultural machinery, farm watering, product transportation e.t.c. For the production of 1kg of bioplastic, 0.5kg of oil fuel is

needed and an energy amount corresponding to the 80% of the energy needed for PE production is consumed. The bioplastics production is sustainable in the sense that reduces the carbon dioxide emissions compared to the conventional plastics production but on the other hand it can lead to deforestation, changes in the water cycle and soil erosion. A possible solution could be the production of bioplastics by agricultural or livestock farming waste, non edible biomass or bio-organisms.

2. The intervention

The awareness raising and attitude change procedure is facilitated by the use of the Care-Know-Do scheme of the CONNECT project [6]. High school students along with their families act as researchers gathering information regarding the polymers used in food packaging and produce predetermined deliverables. The participants in each phase of the applied open schooling framework are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Participants involved in each phase of the care-know-do implementation

Phase	Participants
Care	Instructor, Students, Student Family Members
Know	Instructor, Scientists, Students, Student Family Members
Do	Instructor, Students, Student Family Members

At the care phase, students and their family members are encouraged to follow a two-level approach. At the first level, they familiarize themselves with the notation of the seven recycling symbols as well as with the labels indicating (bio)degradable plastic and associate these symbols with the food and beverage plastic packaging found at their homes. At the second level, they expand their research to prepare lists and make links between different polymers and food/beverage packaging found at supermarkets and foodservice establishments.

In order to boost the awareness raising and the attitude change efficiency of the intervention, comprehensive data and guidelines are provided to the students during the care and know-steps, which are related to the hazardous chemicals that can be released from packaging and contaminate our food. These potential risks may originate from the manufacturing, use or disposal/recycling life-phase of the packaging. The students are actually involved in the investigation of the following issues:

- Why is the use of plastic materials in food packaging/containers so widespread worldwide?
- Which properties of plastics made them so popular in everyday use?
- What information can we extract from the resin identification codes?
- Is temperature, mechanical stress or radiation affecting the safety of plastic food packaging/containers? Are there plastics that withstand high ambient or food temperatures?
- Can plastic food packaging/containers be safely used in conventional ovens, microwave ovens and/or dishwashers?
- How can plastic packaging and plastic containers contaminate our food?
- Can we find other materials to replace plastic materials for food packaging and containers?
- Are biodegradable bioplastics the solution?

The students, realize the threefold origin of hazardous chemicals and microplastics release and are encouraged to adopt a corresponding three level sustainable consumption action: 1. appropriate food packaging selection, 2. sensible use and 3. responsible disposal/recycling. Furthermore, the pros and cons of proposed solutions to the plastics problem, such as usage of recycled, reusable, or bio-based and/or biodegradable plastic, or switching to other materials in food packaging, are investigated.

At the Do-step, the students work in teams to produce deliverables associated with the consumer action guidelines (SDG:3) and a roadmap of sustainable consumption (SDGs:3,12). They disseminate

their findings and outcomes in the form of digital posters and presentations, participate in related conferences and make interventions to the policy makers and/or the chemical industry (SDGs:9,12).

3. The behavior change

An integral part of the attitude-change intervention proposed in this paper is its evaluation. The proposed model is an adaptation of the Transtheoretical Model (TTM) known also as the Stages of Change Model [7]. Based on the identification of the steps of behavior change, it provides an effective framework to describe the status of change implementation. Using checklists and interviews with participating students, the evaluator seeks for evidence regarding their motivation and their ability to change and identifies the stages of change achieved.

Critical to the attitude-change and intervention success assessment, is the post-evaluation of the students' change-maintenance and their determination to follow the goals of sustainable consumption.

The stages of change, accompanied with identifying examples for the case of change in consumer recycling behavior, are the following:

- **Precontemplation** (Not realizing the existence of a problem behavior and the need to be changed: *"I have no intention of starting recycling plastic"*)
- **Contemplation** (Realizing the problem existence but not yet ready to make a change: *"I might start recycling"*)
- **Preparation/Determination** (Getting ready to change: *"I will definitely start recycling"*)
- **Action** (Changing behavior: *"I have started recycling"*)
- **Maintenance** (Maintaining the behavior change: *"Recycling has become an integral part of my lifestyle"*) and sometimes
- **Relapse** (Going back to a previous stage or completely abandoning changes: *"I am no longer recycling since it was a time consuming task"*)

Relapse, as can be seen in Figure 1, is not a state. It is actually a recycling process involving return from the *Maintenance* or *Action* stage to a previous stage.

Figure 1. The Stages of Change (Transtheoretical) Model

In order to assess readiness to change regarding recycling, a set of closed ended questions were developed and are listed in table 3. The students had to respond selecting/receiving the following options/scores: i) Strongly disagree/(-2), ii) Disagree/(-1), iii) Not sure/0, iv) Agree/1, v) Strongly agree/2

Table 3. Assessment of readiness to change. P: Precontemplation, C: Contemplation, A: Action

Items to be scored	Stage of Change
I am trying to recycle more often than I used	A
I am using plastic food packaging but unfortunately I usually ignore recycling	C
Sometimes I think I should start recycling	C
It's a waste of time trying to recycle	P
I don't think I am underestimating recycling	P
I have just recently put recycling in my lifestyle	A
People usually talk about the benefits of recycling, I am already doing something about it	A
I now believe I should think about beginning recycling	C
No-recycling can actually be a problem sometimes	C
Recycling is not a priority for me	P
I am beginning recycling right now	A
There is no reason changing my habits and begin recycling	P

Closed ended questions measuring Maintenance or Relapse as well as questions for the overall evaluation of the intervention are listed in Table 4.

Table 4. The stages of change and overall evaluation. M: Maintenance, R: Relapse

Items to be scored	Stage of Change
1 I feel satisfied taking part in the CONNECT project	-
2 My participation in the CONNECT project enhanced my support to recycling	-
3 Due to the awareness I have gained by my participation in the CONNECT project I am now more likely to check the plastic food packaging labels before purchasing a food product	-
4 One year after my CONNECT experience, recycling has become an integral part of my lifestyle	M/R
5 One year after my CONNECT experience I am regularly checking the food packaging labels before purchasing	M/R
6 I am no longer anxious about checking the labels of plastic food packaging as I was doing during the CONNECT project implementation	R/M
7 I cannot afford the time to continue recycling anymore	R/M
8 My participation at the CONNECT project enhanced my interest about science	-

The overall evaluation of the intervention was also supported by open-ended questions such as:

- Which aspect of the “Plastics and food” educational scenario implementation did you find more difficult or less interesting?
- What was the most interesting or useful feature of the “Plastics and food” educational scenario implementation ?
- Please suggest any improvements to the “Plastics and food” educational scenario implementation

The abovementioned sets of closed and open-ended questions are suitable for determining the stage of change for each student during the intervention as well as after a sufficient time interval (six months, one year) in order to post evaluate the intervention and assess its effectiveness in changing consumer behavior. In our case, post evaluation after one year was implemented yielding encouraging results. In addition, the science capital of the students was found to be enhanced. Students also had the opportunity to become familiar with science and scientific research.

Commenting on the results, it is important to stress out that in the question "My participation in the CONNECT project enhanced my support to recycling" more than half of the students from a typical grade 11 class responded by "Agree" and "Strongly Agree". The participation of a team of students to the Panhellenic Student Conference of the CONNECT project was very fruitful and enhanced their interest in science. This enhanced interest has been detected by the students' responses to open-ended questions. The need for cooperation with students from other schools and other countries was another important issue revealed by the responses to the open-ended evaluation questions.

In order to more accurately evaluate the effectiveness [8] of the intervention and the proposed evaluation scheme, future work should test the intervention in new contexts scaling up and targeting new groups and populations such as, the parents participating in the CONNECT project.

4. Conclusions

We have demonstrated an intervention to high school students towards a sustainable attitude change in consumer behavior in compliance with SDGs of the United Nations' 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. The intervention is based on an educational scenario designed following the care-know-do framework of open schooling of the CONNECT Horizon 2020 project. Students are acting as researchers in a process where families, the educator and scientists are involved.

An evaluation method is proposed and implemented, based in the stages of change model of behavior change. One year after, the intervention post-evaluation is yielding encouraging results regarding the recycling of plastic behavior change and the effectiveness of the intervention. The implemented open schooling framework is found to enhance the science capital of the students and their trust, as well as their positive view, about science and scientific research.

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